

Bound State Quantum Mechanics as a Statistical Theory in Momentum Space?

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Classical statistical mechanics appears to be a statistical theory in momentum space with the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution as the driver. The $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ spatial dependency follows from the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. The reason the MB distribution “exists” in momentum space is that it can be derived solely from two particle scattering with $f(v_1)f(v_2)=f(v_1\prime)f(v_2\prime)$ together with conservation of momentum and kinetic energy i.e. elastic scattering. Maximization of entropy is not needed to derive the MB distribution, although it can be derived in such a manner. Thus, classical statistical mechanics is a theory of many particle scattering in momentum space subject elastic scattering or conservation of kinetic energy.

Bound state quantum mechanics, on the other hand, is usually based on the time-independent Schrodinger equation which is a spatial differential equation. Thus, the focus is on space and spatial derivatives. The wavefunction $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \text{ } f_p \sin(px)$ (or $\cos(px)$ depending on the symmetry) links momentum and space, but one is really concerned with $W(x)$. Density $W(x)W(x)$ is strictly a spatial observable. Furthermore, there is interference because $\sin(px)$ can have positive and negative values and so matters are complicated. For example, the average kinetic energy $[\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m \text{ } f_p \sin(px)]/W(x)$ at a point x , involves some $\sin(px)$ values being positive and others negative, which is difficult to interpret.

In this note, we suggest considering bound state quantum mechanics as a statistical theory in momentum space. Instead of two particle collisions, collisions are occurring with the potential in a similar manner. In quantum mechanics f_p , the momentum wavefunction is the square root of momentum probability. This allows f_p to be positive or negative, unlike $f(v)$ in classical statistical mechanics. These positive and negative values, present even when there is no potential, allow for periodicity, which seems to be central to quantum mechanics. We try to show in this note, that bound state quantum mechanics is also based on conservation of energy at each p level.

It is interesting to note that for the ground state of the quantum oscillator, where there are no humps (the solution is Gaussian in both space and momentum space), the quantum statistical theory yields the same results as classical statistical mechanics.

Classical Statistical Mechanics

Classical statistical mechanics seems to be driven by the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution which is a momentum space distribution based on two particle elastic scattering. Thus, one has

$$f(p_1)f(p_2)=f(p_1\prime)f(p_2\prime) \quad ((1))$$

Thus, the probability for scattering from p_1 and p_2 into p_1' , p_2' is the same as the time reversed process and so there is no change in $f(p$'s) over time. By using conservation of energy, one immediately arrives at the MB distribution as in (1). If a potential $V(x)$, is present, one can modify the result by $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ to link probabilities at x and x_1 . The theory is still one of momentum space collisions. In (2), it is shown that one can write a differential equation for $f(p)$ based on ((1)) and conservation of energy, thus making the theory dependent on only p .

A main idea of equilibrium classical statistical mechanics is that one have a constant temperature everywhere.

Single Particle Quantum Mechanics with No Potential

It seems that important features of quantum mechanics are already present in the analysis of a particle in a box with $V(x)=0$. One has $W(x)=C\sin(px)$ showing that there is a square root of probability which can be positive or negative. This is related to oscillations. The density is $W(x)W(x)$ and shows the consequences of these oscillations. In a momentum space description, one can write $W(x)=C/2i [\exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx)]$. Here one sees that $f_p=C/2i$ for p and $f_{-p}=-C/2i$ for $-p$. Thus, f_p can change sign just like $W(x)$. This suggests oscillations or periodicity in momentum space as well.

Bound State Quantum Mechanics

To obtain bound state quantum mechanics in momentum space, consider the time-independent Schrodinger equation with both $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ written as Fourier series. Then:

$$f_p p^2/2m \exp(ipx) + [\sum_{k+j=p} V_k f_j] \exp(ipx) = E \exp(ipx) \text{ for each } p \quad ((2))$$

One can cancel $\exp(ipx)$ and obtain equations independent of x .

Equation ((2)) looks like a kind of conservation of energy equation, but one can perhaps think of it in a slightly different way. One may consider that for no potential, the solution is given by a linear combination of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. For a potential, one may suggest a linear combination of many different $\exp(ip_i x)$ with p_i being one possible momentum wave. The weights of these $\exp(ip_i x)$ would be f_p which can be positive or negative. This allows for the periodicity present when $V(x)=0$ to carry over into the more complicated case of $V(x)$ not zero. If the f_p 's represent equilibrium weights of the various $\exp(ipx)$, one must be aware that the picture is dynamic, not static. The various $\exp(ipx)$'s should still scatter with the potential (just like two particle scattering in classical statistical mechanics) with the overall weights f_p being unchanged by the scattering. If one tries to write the scattering as a combination of $V(x)W(x)$, both written as a Fourier series, then this combination should be proportional to $f_p \exp(ipx)$ for combinations in $V(x)W(x)$ which yield $[\sum_{k+j=p} V_k f_j] \exp(ipx)$. Furthermore, the scattering should be related to potential energy as $V(x)$ is potential energy. Thus, the existence of ((2)) may not be altogether surprising, but is nevertheless interesting. In ((2)) it argued that potential energy in momentum space is really due to a dynamic system in which different $\exp(ip_i x)$

states combine with $V(x)$ to form $\exp(i p x)$. The energy available for this subset of interactions is:

$E = p^2/2m$. Thus, there is a conservation of energy occurring at the level of each p , which may not have been expected.

The overall average kinetic energy in the bound state is:

$$\sum_p p^2/2m f_p^* f_p \quad ((3))$$

Here there is no interference as in the spatial situation where $[\sum_p p^2/2m f_p \sin(px)]/W(x)$ has both negative and positive terms.

Equation ((2)) can be written as:

$$f_p [\sum_{k+j=p} V_k f_j] = f_p^* f_p [E - p^2/2m] \quad ((4))$$

This is the conservation of energy equation describing the statistical scattering in momentum space which we argue, represents bound state quantum mechanics. (The spatial results are then obtained through a Fourier transform.)

Case of the Ground State of the Quantum Oscillator

It is interesting to note that for the case of $f_p = \exp(-bp^2)$, which is the solution of the ground state oscillator, f_p is strictly positive, just as in the case of classical statistical mechanics. Thus, the oscillations, which are present for higher E_n levels are not found in the ground state and it mimics classical statistical mechanical. In such a case, the right hand side of ((4)) is equal to free energy in momentum space i.e.

$$\sum_p f_p^* f_p E = E \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_p f_p^* f_p (p^2/2m) = -T [-\sum_p f_p^* f_p \ln f_p^* f_p] \quad ((5))$$

If $f_p^* f_p = \exp(-p^2/2mT)$.

Thus, the quantum mechanical bound state statistical condition is related to free energy for the ground state oscillator and $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$ is a stationary result (i.e. related to maximum entropy subject to constraints.) This seems to show how the statistical theory of bound state quantum mechanics in momentum space becomes equivalent to classical statistical mechanics. In general there is no such equivalency because f_p can be positive or negative in quantum mechanics, leading to very different results.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue in this note, that bound state quantum mechanics is a statistical theory in momentum space based on interactions of $\exp(ipx)$ waves with a potential, decomposed in a Fourier series. The weights of the $\exp(ipx)$ in equilibrium, namely f_p , can be positive or negative, just as in the case of no potential, leading to characteristic oscillations in quantum mechanics. Each p wave is governed by a conservation of energy equation in momentum space, given by ((4)). In the case of the ground state oscillator, f_p is positive, and the statistical theory of quantum mechanics mimics that of classical statistical mechanics.

References

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